

IMPROVING STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN BUSINESS FIXED CAPITAL INVESTMENT

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Abstract

Purpose – This article aims to highlight, on the one hand, the factors that determine the demand for investments in fixed capital and which influence the investment decision and on the other hand, the role and importance of this demand (request) for the strategic management of the enterprise.

Methodology/approach - The data sources used in the study are numerous: papers, documents, statistics and information obtained directly from firms. These data have been analyzed and interpreted by the authors.

Findings – This article presents the main investment models that are able to explain the investment behavior of the companies and tests some investment models taking into account the Romanian energy sector. Precisely, the article refers to the activity that carries, according to the classification of activities in the Romanian national economy, the following name: electricity and heat, gas and water. The results obtained from these tests revealed that the demand for investments in fixed capital is not determined by a single factor but by a combination of factors. Our data analysis revealed factors such as: changes in the volume of investments made in the national economy, which occurred in the current period compared to the previous one, changes in the level of tangible fixed assets currently existing in the activity compared to the previous period, the current average interest rate and partially, the volume of industrial production obtained in this economic activity field.

Research limitations/implications – The limits of this research are given by the analysis of a single field of activity, namely the activity that bears the name: electricity and heat, gas and water.

Practical implications – Practical implications of this study, regarding the strategic management of an enterprise, are related to analysis, knowledge and anticipation of the demand for fixed capital investments. Based on an investment model, compatible with the economic activity carried out, allows the enterprise to take concrete measures, choosing the best global and partial strategies to ensure a certain competitive advantage.

Originality/value – There are two main contributions of this paper: the first one refers to a model able to determine which are the main determinants of the demand for fixed capital investments in the analyzed activity field, after testing several investments; the second one, is to highlight the role and the importance of this demand for the company strategic management.

Key words: Investments, demand, firms, strategic management, decisions.

Introduction

In the equation of the development and economic growth of a societies, investments are the driving forces on which human efforts are directed towards improving the economic results. Through investments, the increase and modernization of fixed capital is realized, with immediate effects on the increase of the labor productivity and of the economic performances.

The role and the importance of the investment demand on the economy, from a generally point of view and upon each enterprise have been analyzed over time, by the world's great economists. For example, J. M. Keynes highlighted the importance of demand on the evolution of the economy and on production, postulating that aggregate demand determines the level of combined production or output.

Investments can be divided into three main categories: residential investment, inventory investment and business fixed investment. This article analyses only business fixed investment and the importance of the strategic management involving business success.

Business fixed investment involve funds used to produce goods and services or to increase production capacity. This kind of investment can be decomposed into equipment, structures, and intellectual property. The stock of machines or plants represents fixed capital. Business fixed investment is an important component of aggregate demand and it is the most volatile element. Investment decisions of firms have implication at the macro level and at the micro level of the economy. At the macro level, they have implications for capital market development, interest rates and regulation. At the micro level, such decisions affect capital structure and firm growth.

For a company that the demand for fixed capital investments must be analyzed considering all the factors that may influence this request. The strategic management of the company has the task of quantifying the role and importance of each factor, making at the right time, the investment decision that will provide them, a certain competitive advantage over other competitors.

The most important theory concerning business fixed investment demand

According to the neoclassical theory, business fixed investment is determined by the cost of capital and by marginal product of capital. In turn, the cost of capital depends mainly on the tax rate, the interest rate and the rate of amortization of fixed capital. The cost of the capital reflects the costs of each source of financing, respectively the average cost of financial resources that the company uses (Drob, 2009).

The cost of capital reflects the costs of each source of financing, respectively the average cost of financial resources that the company uses. The investment decision must be based on a comparison of the cost of capital used to finance the investment with the expected return on that investment, or between the cost of using a new unit of capital and the marginal income generated by its use. If the expected return on investment is higher than the cost of capital used, or if the marginal income is higher than the cost of using an additional unit of capital, then the investment decision can be made. Marginal product of capital is the additional product made by using an additional unit of the same capital. In turn, the marginal productivity of capital is determined by the volume of labor and the labor technology used. The higher the volume of labor is, the more efficient manufacturing technology is, the bigger it is the marginal productivity of capital.

Bischoff, C. W., Bosworth, B. and Hall, R. (1971) has been developed an extension of the neoclassical model, emphasizing that investments are more sensitive to changes in the level of production than to changes in the cost of capital. J. M. Keynes proposed another approach to explain the investment behavior of firms. According to this approach, the incentive to invest can be attributed to two factors: the marginal efficiency of capital and the interest rate. According to Keynes investment decisions are taken by comparing the marginal efficiency of capital with the interest rate (Drob, 2009). If the marginal efficiency of capital is higher than the interest rate, the firm investment decisions is to invest.

Another theory, which aims to analyze and explain how the demand for investment in fixed capital manifests itself is that of the investment accelerator. This theory is often associated with Keynes's approach but was first proposed by Maurice Clark (1917) and later developed by Hollis Chenery (1952), Leendert Koyck (1954) and others. The investment accelerator model establishes that the demand for investments in capital goods is determined by the demand for production made based on those goods. The effect of the accelerator principle translates into net investments during the period of increasing sales of consumer goods and through net divestments during periods of crisis (Drob and Serbu, 2010). Robert Eisner and colleagues reviewed the accelerator theory, considering profit. Eisner believes that investments in capital goods depend on sales, depreciation, and profit. Other studies related to the field of investments have highlighted the fact that the company's cash flow is also an important determinant of investments (Drob and Serbu, 2010).

Neoclassical investment theory and accelerator theory do not consider signals given by the market when making decisions about fixed capital investments. To remove this disadvantage, William Brainard and James Tobin developed a theory (Theory "q") that tries to explain the demand for investments considering the market value of firms' assets established on the capital market. This model starts from

the premise that the demand for fixed capital investments varies in proportion to the ratio between the market value of the company's assets and the replacement value of the capital held by that company. This ratio is known as the "q" factor (Eklund, 2013).

The neoclassical theory of investment has another vulnerability: it starts from the assumption that investments are reversible and have a neutral risk. Investments in fixed capital are irreversible, because through the disinvestment process only a small part of the capital initially invested is recovered and the recovery process supposes a certain period of time. The risk-neutral investment assumption is also unacceptable because any investment involves a risk dose. Because investment involves risk, general expectations about the future will influence an investment decision of the firm. Recent investment research has highlighted that investments decisions must consider another factor, namely uncertainty (Dixit and Pindyck, 1994). Uncertainty is generally caused by macroeconomic factors, such as: changes in state fiscal policy, interest rates or exchange rates, and so on. This uncertainty can refer to the future evolution of demand, profit, sales, prices of inputs or outputs, etc.

Since investments are irreversible, investment decisions should be postponed until there is sufficient information on market development. Generally, the cumulative effect of uncertainty and irreversibility is reflected in the decline of current investments and the postponement of investments projects.

Own study concerning business fixed investment demand

For the analysis of the demand for fixed capital investments, we chose as economic field of study the power energy sector, focused on the activity named, according to the classification of activities in the Romanian national economy: electricity and heat, gas and water. The purpose of the applicative part is to develop and analyses different models regarding the demand for fixed capital investments and, finally, to choose the best model able to explain the evolution of this demand within the analyzed activity. In the carried-out research, we started from the hypothesis that the request is fully transformed into investments made in the targeted economic activity. Taking into account certain economic legitimacies and the statistical data available to the analyzed sector, two economic variables were selected for the construction of the models: first one: investments related to "electricity and heat, gas and water" (considered dependent variable), and second one: GDP, interest rate (r), total investments made in the national economy (IT), industrial production (Y) and existing tangible fixed assets (K) within the analyzed economic activity (considered independent variables). The dependent variable (I) - investments made in the economic activity "electricity and heat, gas and water" - refers mainly to investments in capital goods, materialized in expenses for the purchase of equipment, means of transport and other expenses for the creation of new fixed assets and for the reconstruction of existing ones in this sector.

It was designed and analyzed 16 models that contain, in a certain combination, the variables considered:

$$M_1: I_t = a_0 + a_1 Y_t + u_t$$

$$M_2: I_t = a_0 + a_1 Y_t + a_2 r_t + u_t$$

$$M_3: I_t = a_0 + a_1 K_t + a_2 Y_t + a_3 r_t + u_t$$

$$M_4: I_t = a_0 + a_1 IT_t + a_2 K_t + a_3 Y_t + a_4 r_t + u_t$$

$$M_5: I_t = a_0 + a_1 PIB_t + a_2 IT_t + a_3 K_t + a_4 Y_t + a_5 r_t + u_t$$

$$M_6: I_t = a_0 + a_1 I_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$M_7: I_t = a_0 + a_1 I_{t-1} + a_2 Y_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$M_8: I_t = a_0 + a_1 I_{t-1} + a_2 K_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$M_9: I_t = a_0 + a_1 I_{t-1} + a_2 K_{t-1} + a_3 IT_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$M_{10}: I_t = a_0 + a_1 PIB_{t-1} + a_2 I_{t-1} + a_3 K_{t-1} + a_4 IT_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$M_{11}: I_t = a_0 + a_1 K_t + a_2 I_{t-1} + a_3 K_{t-1} + a_4 IT_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$M_{12}: I_t = a_0 + a_1K_t + a_2K_{t-1} + a_3IT_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$M_{13}: I_t = a_0 + a_1IT_t + a_2K_t + a_3K_{t-1} + a_4IT_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$M_{14}: I_t = a_0 + a_1IT_t + a_2K_t + a_3r_t + a_4K_{t-1} + a_5IT_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$M_{15}: I_t = a_0 + a_1IT_t + a_2K_t + a_3Y_t + a_4r_t + a_5K_{t-1} + a_6IT_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$M_{16}: I_t = a_0 + a_1PIB_t + a_2IT_t + a_3K_t + a_4Y_t + a_5r_t + a_6K_{t-1} + a_7IT_{t-1} + u_t$$

Where:

I_t, I_{t-1} – investments made in the economic activity "electricity and heat, gas and water" in year "t", and "t-1", respectively.

IT_t, IT_{t-1} – total investments made in the national economy in year "t", and "t-1", respectively.

Y_t, Y_{t-1} – industrial production related to the economic activity "electricity and heat, gas and water" in year "t", and "t-1", respectively.

PIB_t, PIB_{t-1} – GDP in year "t" and "t-1", respectively.

K_t, K_{t-1} – existing tangible assets within the economic activity "electricity and heat, gas and water" in year "t", and "t-1", respectively.

r_t – average interest rate in year t.

u_t – random variable.

The random variable, also called residual or random, encompasses all variables, except exogenous ones, which, even if they influence the resultant variable, are not specified in the model. In the present study, both for estimating the parameters of the designed models and for calculating statistical indicators, we used the Statistics software. This software allows complex analysis of statistical data. The analysis consists, among others, in establishing the regression equations, in calculating some indicators and some statistical variables, in applying statistical tests, drawing correlation graphs between certain variables, making predictions, etc. Among the calculated statistical indicators is the coefficient of multiple determination R. This indicator measures the proportion of variation of the dependent variable explained by the regression equation. The square of this coefficient (R^2) can take values between 0 and 1. The closer the size of R^2 to 1 is, the better the variation of the dependent variable is explained by means of the regression equation. When R^2 takes values close to zero, then the chosen model to explain the dependent variable is considered inadequate.

Among the statistical tests we chose the "t", "F" and the Durbin-Watson test. The "t" (Student) test is used to check the significance of the model parameters. The "F" test is used to verify the significance of the model. This test indicates if the results obtained on the model are significant, with a certain significance threshold. The Durbin-Watson test is used to test the error interdependence hypothesis.

Among the analyzed models, the model that give the best explanation for the variation of investments, respectively the demand for capital goods, is the model M_{15} ($M_{15}: I_t = a_0 + a_1IT_t + a_2K_t + a_3Y_t + a_4r_t + a_5K_{t-1} + a_6IT_{t-1} + u_t$), since from all the models developed in this paper, it has the highest value for the statistical variable "F" and for the coefficient of multiple determination R^2 ($R^2 = 0.862164$).

In a concise form, the above model can be presented in the following form:

$$I_t = a_0 + a_1\Delta IT_t + a_2\Delta K_t + a_3Y_t + a_4r_t + u_t$$

where:

$$\Delta IT_t = IT_t - IT_{t-1} \text{ and}$$

$$\Delta K_t = K_t - K_{t-1}.$$

This form of the M15 model makes easier to interpret the results obtained on its own. According to this model, the current demand for fixed capital investments in the economic activity "electricity and heat, gas and water" is dependent on changes that appears in the volume of investments in national economy, which occurred in the current period compared to the previous one. It is also dependent of the changes in fixed assets currently existing in the analyzed activity compared to the previous period, of the current average interest rate and, partially, of the volume of industrial production obtained in this economic activity. More precisely, the dependence is positive towards the changes of investments within the national economy and negative at the variation of the level of tangible fixed assets afferent to the field of activity targeted and towards the average rate of active interests. For an enterprise in this field of activity, these empirical results shows that the demand for fixed capital investments must increase during the boom of the national economy, when there are positive changes, from one period of time to another, in terms of regarding the level of total investments and / or when the average interest rate is low, respectively decreases in times of crisis or at times characterized by a high average interest rate. At the same time, this demand must be permanently correlated with the variation of the level of tangible fixed assets, from one period to another, both at the economic activity level and at the enterprise level.

The role and the importance of the study

The usefulness of this study can be found in the strategic management of the company. In the vision of modern strategic management, the approach of the enterprise-environment relationship implies the anticipation and modification of the evolution of the external environment by training, coordination and adequate targeting of own resources, in order to achieve a competitive advantage. This advantage can be obtained by the efficient use of new fixed assets, new technologies, leading to an output as high as possible per input unit etc. At the same time, the achievement of the competitive advantage can be obtained by ensuring an optimal stock of capital, both quantitatively and qualitatively. This means triggering the investment or divestment process whenever the current capital stock is different from the optimal one. In this case, the demand for fixed capital investment must be in line with the optimal level of fixed capital. Even if there is a continuous gap between the current level of capital and the optimal one, managers must act permanently to reduce it.

Some companies expect to increase their demand for industrial or consumer goods first, and then adjust their demand for capital goods accordingly. Such an approach is fundamentally wrong because only companies that anticipate both the demand for the own goods and the capital goods needed to be achieved, can make effective decisions regarding the timing of the investments or divestments process in capital goods, thus obtaining a competitive advantage over other competitors (Simionescu and Drob, 2001). For an enterprise, the demand for fixed capital investments must not be analyzed in a static way but in a dynamic one, by considering all the implications generated by its links with the external environment. The strategic management of the enterprise has the task of quantifying the role and importance of each factor, which leave traces on its activity, to ensure a certain competitive advantage.

Investment theory and practice have proposed several investment models that incorporate some of these factors and can provide information on how the demand for fixed capital investments can evolve. For the strategic management of the enterprise, the knowledge of such information is important because the changes that occur regarding the level of demand for fixed capital investments exercise a strong influence on the production capacity of the enterprise, the need for staff, the balance of payments, etc. This means that, when designing the global and partial strategies of the enterprise, the multitude of consequences generated by the change in the demand for fixed capital investments on the specific fields of the enterprise (production, human resources, financial field, etc.) must also be taken into account. The outcomes that appears considering the demand for investments in capital goods when the company's strategies are fundament upon those considerate, are found in a more efficient allocation of resources, in reduced production costs etc. and finally, in increasing the enterprise competitiveness.

Discussion and conclusions

The role and importance of the demand, in general and demand for fixed capital investment has been the subject of several researches conducted in the contemporary period. The unanimous conclusion of the authors who studied this issue is that demand plays an essential role in the market economy

equation, more important than the supply. Investment theories and models developed over time have shown that the demand for fixed capital investment is dependent on several variables. These variables include the cost of the capital, interest rate, output, marginal product of the capital, marginal efficiency of the capital, uncertainty, cash flow, profit, “q” factor etc. Depending on the authors, the models developed contain one or more factors that have a greater or lesser importance.

Among the models analyzed by the authors, the model that best explains the variation of investments, respectively the demand for fixed capital investments, is the model that has as the following variables: the first one refers to changes in the volume of investments made in the national economy, occurred in the current period. The second one refers to the level of tangible fixed assets currently existing within the analyzed activity compared to the previous period. The third one refers to the current average interest rate and the volume of industrial production obtained within the analyzed economic activity. For the strategic management of an enterprise, the analysis, knowledge and anticipation of the demand for fixed capital investments, based on an investment model compatible with the economic activity carried out, can allow the enterprise to take concrete measures regarding the choice of the best global and partial strategies, in order to provide a certain competitive advantage.

References

Drob, C.

2011

“General and specific aspects regarding the relationship between uncertainty, irreversibility and investment”, Journal of Engineering Studies and Research, Bacău – Volume 17, No. 4, pp. 41-44, ISSN: 2068-7559.

2010

“The comparative analysis of the investment models from empirical point of view”, Annals of the Oradea University, Fascicle of Management and Technological Engineering, Volume IX (XIX), pp. 4149-4152, ISSN 1583-0691.

2009

“Investiții directe de capital”, Editura Alma Mater, Bacău, ISBN 978-606-527-016-9.

2008

“Multifactorial models of investment with financial variables”, Annals of the Oradea University, Fascicle of Management and Technological Engineering, Volume XVII (VII), pag. 2144-2147, ISSN 1583-0691.

Drob, C., Șerbu, R. S.

2010

“Investment models that capture the accelerator effect”, Revista economică – Journal of Economic-Financial Theory and Practice, Volum 1, Nr 6(53), pp. 218-221, ISSN: 1582-6260.

Drob, C., Zichil. V., Buzoianu-Cârțiță, C.

2018

“Behind making decisions: an overview regarding Romanian managers”, Conference Proceedings of the 6th RMEE2018 - Performance Management or Management Performance, Todesco Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca, pp. 335-339, ISSN: 2247-8639.

Dixit, A., Pindyck, R.

1994

“Investment under uncertainty”, Princeton University Press, ISBN: 9780691034102.

Eklund, J.E.

2013

“Theories of Investment: a theoretical review with empirical applications”, Swedish Entrepreneurship Forum, Workingpaper 22.

Simionescu, Gh., Drob, C.

2001

“Present evolution of firm organization and management”, Proceedings of 2nd International Conference on the Management of Technological Change, Technical University “Gh. Asachi” Iași, pp. 107-112.